

AGE CHARACTERISTICS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATSIYA: Chet tilini yosh guruhları (kattalar, o'smirlar va maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar) bo'yicha o'rgatish o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega, shuningdek, katta yoshdagi o'quvchilarning ba'zi atributları bu vazifani osonlashtiradigan, boshqalari esa qiyinchiliklar manbai bo'lgan usul va tamoyillarga ega. Ushbu tadqiqot chet tillarini yosh guruhlariga qarab o'rganish va o'rgatish bilan bog'liq asosiy masalalarni ko'rib chiqish, shuningdek, o'qitish jarayonini optimallashtirish uchun yosh guruhları xususiyatlarini kapitallashtirish usullarini ko'rsatishga qaratilgan. Birinchi navbatda til o'rganishning umumiy tamoyillari muhokama qilinadi, undan keyin chet tillarini yoshga qarab o'qitishning o'ziga xosligi, shuningdek, eng samarali usul va strategiyalarni tanlash masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, tamoyil, yosh guruhları, metod, strategiya, ingliz tili, tahlil, instruktorlar, muloqot ishtirokchilari, o'qituvchi.

АННОТАЦИЯ Преподавание иностранного языка в соответствии с возрастными группами (взрослые, подростки и дети дошкольного/школьного возраста) имеет свою специфику, а также методы и принципы, при этом некоторые характеристики взрослых учащихся облегчают эту задачу, а другие являются источником трудностей. Целью данного исследования является предоставление обзора ключевых вопросов, касающихся изучения и преподавания иностранного языка в соответствии с возрастными группами, а также выделение способов, с помощью которых характеристики возрастных групп могут быть использованы для оптимизации процесса обучения. В первую очередь обсуждаются общие принципы изучения языка, за которыми следует рассмотрение вопросов, касающихся специфики преподавания иностранных языков в соответствии с возрастом, а также выбора наиболее эффективных методов и стратегий.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, принцип, возрастные группы, метод, стратегия, английский язык, анализ, преподаватели, коммуникация, участники, учитель.

ABSTRACT Teaching a foreign language according to age groups (adults, adolescents and preschool/school children) has its own specificity, as well as methods and principles with some attributes of adult learners being facilitative of this task and others constituting a source of difficulties. This study is aimed to provide an overview of key issues relevant to foreign language learning and teaching according to age groups, as well as highlights the ways in which the characteristics of age groups can be capitalized upon to optimize the teaching process. In the first place, common principles of language learning are discussed, which is followed by a consideration of issues concerning the specificity of teaching foreign languages according to age, as well as choice of the most effective methods and strategies.

Keywords: foreign language, principle, age groups, method, strategy, English language, analysis, instructors, communication, participants, teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Before starting to discuss the issues of teaching foreign languages according to age groups, it is necessary to define these categories, as well as note the distinctive characteristics of each group. It should be noted that this task itself may cause a serious challenge. Our study included three age groups: adults, adolescents and preschool/school children. So, for example, according to the criteria of Komorowska (2003), the group of adults includes individuals aged 19 and over, who have the ability to read and write, use abstract thinking, and possess intellectual and social maturity. With regard to the issues of teaching a foreign language in this age group, the author notes that this aspect is less problematic compared to the group of adolescents and preschool/schoolchildren. The teenage group of students is represented by adolescents aged 13 to 19.

Teaching English to Adults

For the majority of adults, the study of the foreign language does not play a key role. For those who study the language as a requirement in bachelor and master's programs there is no immediate value of foreign languages in their lives, and unfortunately, it usually leads to obtaining the language course required to complete their studies. As a result, there is simple satisfaction that students with basic knowledge of foreign language can use their communication skills, for example, when they go on vacation abroad. For adult learners who need the foreign language for their future.

Teaching foreign languages to adults is rather a serious challenge that brings many opportunities, but at the same time constitutes the need to overcome serious difficulties. This is because, on the one hand, adults have qualities that can increase their chances for obtaining success in language learning, such as superior cognitive skills, the ability to self-govern, persistence, and at least significant motivation, but on the other hand, they are more prone to emotional outbursts, and quickly become discouraged. Therefore, to provide effective teaching, teachers should try to capitalize on the strengths of this age group and take steps to minimize the harmful effects of their weaknesses. The students in this age group are able to achieve a high level of proficiency in the target language, and it can certainly be guaranteed that some of them will be successful, regardless of whether this success equates to basic communication skills such as comprehension of specialized texts, or advanced productive knowledge and use of the foreign language in various situations.

Teaching English to Adolescents

Adolescents, being the most demanding and difficult, as mentioned above, group of learners, require a systematic option of teaching. It is related to the fact that adolescents go through a very stormy period, which includes significant psychological and physical changes. Therefore, the teacher is responsible for providing the best useful way for learning language. In order to optimize the teaching process, the teacher may apply many different methods and techniques suitable for teenagers.

It is recommended to apply methods of teaching which will emphasize all four learning aspects - listening, speaking, reading and writing, as well as make a stress on the communicative competence. The Direct Method and Counseling Language Learning are most appropriate methods of teaching English to adolescents. The Direct Method teaches the foreign language in the same way as students learn the mother tongue. Besides, this method can afford students to think in English rather than in their mother tongue. Starting to express the thoughts by means of English, they surely can acquire fluency in speaking better. Students will be able to speak or write in foreign language without the necessity to translating them into mother tongue. Adolescents are very bound with their peers and this method gives them a chance to work together. Students know about their strengths and weaknesses and like to work as a group. The Method of Grammar Translation is effective in case if the adolescents are required to know basic grammar rules. This method gives learners a base and force them to develop communicative skills. Students who are taught successfully will have the ability to translate even difficult texts from their native language into English.

Teaching English to Preschool and School Children

It is well-known that children (aged 3-6 and 7-12) are very much orientated in their minds around the "here and now" and directly visible/perceivable environment. Grammatical rules/explanations are usually lost on them, as are somewhat "adult" notions of what is correct and what isn't. They develop well when given plenty of examples and patterns to follow. They tend to have a much shorter attention span and need activities that capture their immediate interest. They also need much in the way of "sensory input" - that is, they need to have many or all of their five senses stimulated at once. While generally less inhibited than adults in terms of experimenting with new language, they tend to have more fragile egos and can be very sensitive to their peers.

According to Piaget's theory of cognitive development, preschool children are in the preoperational stage of intelligence so learning process can be realized through experience with concrete materials such as objects, pictures, stories, and videos.

For the 1-2 class learners at school the EL is presented, practiced and learned through speaking and listening. For these learners, effective classroom strategies have traditionally involved use of plays, songs, rhymes and stories with repeated language structures. One way to capture attention of children under 7-8 years and keep them engaged in activities is to supplement the activities with lots of brightly colored visuals, toys, puppets, or objects to match the stories that a teacher tells or songs that a teacher sings.

CONCLUSION

Thus, summarizing the above discussed we may conclude that all foreign language learners despite their age groups need appropriate and useful approaches and methods applied. Concrete materials helps them understand and process the meaning. Teachers provide a range of activities to get learners' attention and arouse constant interest. For preschool/school learners, physical activities such as walking, running, jumping, dancing and climbing contribute positively to learning when coordinated with language. Age is the important factor in language acquisition both in first language and foreign language. Studies show that early language acquisition is necessary to reach proficiency in language. As a final note, further research is necessary on children' learning process and their learning styles, as there is a limited number of studies on future effects of early start in acquiring the foreign language rather than the second language.

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